

Sectoral brief

November 2025

Reducing Risks Together: Multi-hazards and multi-risks in the finance sector

Executive summary & Recommendations

Multi-hazards are a known risk with the finance sector – flooding from hurricanes, and the impact of that flooding, is explicitly modelled by the catastrophe models; flooding associated with European windstorms is accounted for when calculating the losses from windstorms; and hazards after an earthquake are also included, e.g. landslide, fire. These multi-hazards are also considered static when considering the impact of climate change, even though projections show an increase in the amount of moisture and thus potential flooding.

As insurance losses continue to increase (Aon 2025 Climate and Catastrophe Insights Report) there is a need to consider the interaction between all perils, globally, both modelled and unmodelled. Recent insurance losses have highlighted the importance of multi-hazard considerations, e.g. European windstorm Eunice (2022), US Hurricane Helene (2024), and US Hurricane Milton (2024), which all saw significant flood contributions.

The results from MYRIAD-EU have shown there's a lot more complexity that needs to be considered when looking to model, and quantify the impact from, multi-hazards and multi-risks. The work within MYRIAD-EU has not only highlighted the dependencies between the perils (multi-hazards) it has also provided a methodology and toolkit to explore these multi-hazards.

There is an increasing need for the finance sector to be able to quantify the impact of multi-hazards and multi-risks. Previously it has been difficult to define these impacts; the work from MYRIAD-EU will significantly help this process due to the methodology and toolkits.

Recommendations:

- There is a need to model multi-hazards in catastrophe models, explicitly identifying the relative contribution of each hazard to the total risk, as seen for flooding from hurricanes, but for other perils, e.g. European windstorms and flooding.
- Vulnerability is often assumed to be static within the catastrophe models, especially for extreme weather events. Results from MYRIAD-EU have shown the time dependence of vulnerability that should be included in catastrophe models.
- Multi-hazards and multi-risks will cross multiple insurance lines: property, business interruption and life. By improving our understanding of multi-risks, it may be possible to identify solutions to reduce the cross-line impact.
- The spatial and temporal elements of multi-risks need to be considered when reviewing risk diversification.
- Catastrophe models should allow for a clearer distinction of the impacts from multi-hazards.

Context

Flooding associated with wind events has always been a known risk. US hurricane Katrina in 2005 saw larger losses associated with flooding than the wind loss, due to the collapse of the levees. More recently, we saw European windstorm Eunice (2022) cause significant flood losses in Europe, whilst the wind-component of the loss was much smaller. US hurricane Helene (2024) saw larger losses due to flooding than wind, which were then made worse when US hurricane Milton followed soon after.

For US hurricanes, we now model the flood losses due to a hurricane as well as the wind losses. However, each hurricane is modelled separately, with the impacts of previous hurricanes not considered. Thus, when US hurricane Milton passed over soon after US hurricane Helene, the already wet conditions, and high river flows, were not modelled. Flooding associated with European windstorms is not modelled, with the catastrophe models physically modelling only the wind component of the peril. It is known that slow-moving European windstorms can result in significant flooding, which was highlighted by European windstorm Eunice in 2022. The flood losses are typically included in the windstorm losses, with the catastrophe models calibrating their losses to include this aggregation.

These events consider only the immediate, and direct multi-hazard components of natural hazards. Longer timescales and multi-risks, here considered to be a loss event that results in subsequent loss events (landslide following flooding), are rarely considered or modelled. With climate change not only changing the nature of multi-hazards (e.g., European windstorms getting wetter (Bloomfield et al., 2023)), but also resulting in multi-hazards starting to impact the finance sector more, there is a need to start considering multi-hazard risks. Before these can be modelled, the scale and nature of multi-hazards, and how multi-risks interact, need to be understood to fully assess the impact on the finance sector.

The MYRIAD-EU project is designed to address the aforementioned challenges. Our vision is to catalyse the paradigm shift required to move towards a multi-risk, multi-sector, systemic approach to risk assessment and management. To achieve this, the overall aim is to develop forward-looking disaster risk reduction pathways in five Pilot EU regions: Danube, Scandinavia, North Sea, Veneto, Canary Islands. Within these Pilots, we assess trade-offs and synergies of various strategies across sectors. These sectors are: energy, ecosystems & forestry, finance, food & agriculture, tourism, and transport & infrastructure. Within the project, we develop tools and methods to allow us to better assess multi-hazard-risk within these sectors. The project is funded by Horizon 2020, and runs between 2021-2025.

Applications of MYRIAD-EU results

One of the barriers to incorporating a multi-hazard or multi-risk view into the finance sector is the lack of a clear definitions, which is critical to understand how these events may impact the sector. Whilst the insurance sector would define these events based on loss experience, and will vary between re-insurance contracts, the basis of the definition, and any challenge of the definition, we would look to academia to provide the insights.

The handbook of definitions developed by MYRIAD-EU (Gill et al., 2022), and the wiki portal [Disaster Risk Gateway](#), are excellent resources for us to get these definitions, with the added benefit that there are definitions from multiple industry sectors and academic views. This provides context to the definitions as well as an understanding of the potential applicability, or limitations, of the definitions to the finance sector.

Multi-Hazard	The selection of multiple major hazards that the country faces, and the specific contexts where hazardous events may occur simultaneously, cascadingly or cumulatively over time, and taking into account the potential interrelated effects.	UNDRR (2016)	See also: Hazard, Section 3.1
Multi-Hazard Risk	Risk generated from multiple hazards and the interrelationships between these hazards (but not considering interrelationships on the vulnerability level).	Zschau (2017)	See also: Hazard; Hazard Interrelationships; Multi-Hazard; Disaster Risk; Vulnerability
Multi-Risk	Risk generated from multiple hazards and the interrelationships between these hazards (and considering interrelationships on the vulnerability level).	Zschau (2017)	See also: Hazard; Multi-Hazard; Disaster Risk; Vulnerability; Section 3.3
Multi-Layer Single	More than one hazards are considered, but not the interrelationships between these (i.e., they are treated as discrete, independent).	Gill & Malamud (2014); Zschau (2017)	See also: Section 3.1
Multi-Hazard Event Sets	A list of multi-hazard events over a given time period.	WP5 (MYRIAD-EU)	See also: Multi-Hazard

Excerpt from the handbook (Gill et al., 2022), which discusses how multi-hazard and multi-hazard risk could be defined.

The Disaster Risk Gateway wiki portal provides additional tools and methods that can be used for assessing multi-hazards and multi-risks. MYRIAD-EU also produced a [repository for multi-hazard storylines](#), which provides material that will help with our definition of these events, specifically historic case studies and the thought process behind how specific events were defined as either multi-

hazard or multi-risk. The insurance industry will look to use historic events, and their associated losses, as a guide to define them as either multi-hazard or multi-risk. Thus, the case studies are crucial to help us develop our view on these events, and the context to the definition allows us to refine our view for specific use cases.

For the finance sector to build out a comprehensive view of multi-hazard risk, or multi-risk, we need to have a global view, and how all the different individual hazards, or risks, are correlated. The work by Claassen et al. (2023) – the MYRIAD Hazard Event Sets Algorithm (MYRIAD-HESA) – has provided both an invaluable tool that can be used within the finance sector to build out this view based on our own definitions of events and hazards of interest, as well as a comprehensive global view of multi-hazards and multi-risks MYRIAD-Hazard Event Sets Dataset (MYRIAD-HES) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: the most frequent multi-hazards and multi-risks globally from the MYRIAD-HES datasets (Claassen et al., 2023).

A key finding for the finance sector from the Claassen et al. (2023) paper is the hazards which are not paired, although the focus of the work was on correlated pairs as shown in Figure 2. From a reinsurance perspective, where the aim is to diversify the risk within a given portfolio (i.e., find areas with low risk to mitigate areas of high risk), this type of information could be extremely useful when reviewing reinsurance portfolios.

The finance sector is starting to evaluate the impacts of this work, to get an improved view of the multi-risks posed by multi-hazards that may have not been understood. This work will allow for a more robust view of multi-risks and the impact they have on the finance sector. Incorporating this work will provide a more informed view to assess risk.

Figure 2: number of hazard pairs within each geography, also showing hazards which are not paired – from the MYRIAD-HES dataset (Claassen et al., 2023).

Recommendations

- Multi-hazards, and their relevance and impact on the finance sector, is often overlooked and not considered a significant contributor to the risk. However, as vulnerability changes and climate change impacts the nature of multi-hazards, this may no longer be the case.
- There is a need to model multi-hazards in catastrophe models, explicitly identifying the relative contribution of each hazard to the total risk, as seen for flooding from hurricanes, but for other perils, e.g. European windstorms and flooding.
- Vulnerability is often assumed to be static within the catastrophe models, especially for extreme weather events. Results from MYRIAD-EU have shown the time dependence of vulnerability that should be included in catastrophe models.

- Multi-hazards and multi-risks will cross multiple insurance lines: property, business interruption and life. By improving our understanding of multi-risks, it may be possible to identify solutions to reduce the cross-line impact.

- The spatial and temporal elements of multi-risks need to be considered when reviewing risk diversification.
- Catastrophe models should allow for a clearer distinction of the impacts from multi-hazards.

List of resources

References

- Aon, 2025. Climate and Catastrophe Insight, 2025-climate-catastrophe-insight.pdf
- Bloomfield et al., 2023. Co-occurring wintertime flooding and extreme wind over Europe, from daily to seasonal timescales, Weather and Climate Extremes, 39, 100550, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wace.2023.100550>.
- Claassen, J.N., Ward, P.J., Daniell, J. et al. 2023. A new method to compile global multi-hazard event sets. Scientific Reports, 13, 13808, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-40400-5>.
- Gill, J.C. et al., 2022. Handbook of Multi-Hazard, Multi-Risk Definitions and Concepts. MYRIAD-EU Deliverable 1.2, doi:10.5281/zenodo.7135137.

For more information

- info@myriadproject.eu
adrian.champion@aon.com
nyas.madappatt@aon.com
- <https://www.myriadproject.eu/>
- https://twitter.com/Myriad_EU
- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/myriad-eu-project/>

Authors

- Dr Adrian Champion
- Dr Niyas Madappatt

Other linked resources

References

- Disaster Risk Gateway: https://disasterriskgateway.net/index.php/Main_Page
- Storylines Repository: <https://dashboard.myriadproject.eu/storylines-repository/>